

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SEBABI****FIRST NAME: FRANCIS ONEN****PROGRAM CODE: DARM****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021,15-23)
2. Applying the American English version (EUCLID 2021, 25-32)
3. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)
4. Avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
5. Referencing (EUCLID 2021, 11)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING**1) INTRODUCTION**

I have found that if I am to correctly, consistently, and coherently write good essays, I should consider several aspects of the essay. In this work, I have described and internalized five concepts: punctuation, language variants for the English world, style guide, plagiarism, and referencing. In all these, I carefully assembled crafted writing pieces to portray and enhance my understanding of the concepts in academic writing.

2) PUNCTUATIONS

Using punctuation marks correctly can enhance the clarity of academic essays. As a general rule, necessary punctuation marks should be used (EUCLID 2021, 16). Some examples of punctuations are apostrophes; brackets consisting of round brackets, square brackets, angle, and curly brackets; bullet points; colon; semicolon; comma; m-dash; n-

dash; hyphen; ellipsis; full stop; exclamation mark; and question mark (EUCLID 2021, 16-24). These punctuations are used in different situations when writing. For example, when using apostrophes, I find it better to avoid simply adding apostrophes and “s” to the name that ends with “z” to denote that person’s possessions. Instead of writing Suarez’s style of playing as easier to learn, I would write as the style of playing of Suarez is easier to learn to cite an example. Nonetheless, the reasons why we use punctuation are varied.

In academic essay, the following are some of the reasons for using punctuations: apostrophes are used to indicate possessions and contractions; round brackets are used in place of a pair of dashes or commas around a non-defining phrase; square brackets are used to enclose comments, corrections, references or translations by a subsequent authors or authors; angle and curly brackets are usually not in academic writing but in technical sense such as in mathematics; bullet points are used listing items; colon is used to introduce a subclause that follows logically the text preceding it, unlike semicolon which links two related parts of a sentence in which neither depends on other and, otherwise each can stand on its own in complete sentence, additionally semicolon can also be used in complicated sentence for purpose of making it more explicit; comma is used in pair in non-defining clause for the purpose of adding description; n-dash is employed in pairs to replace commas or round brackets, it usually surrounded by spaces; hyphen is used in adjectival phrase before a noun; ellipsis shows that some text is missing, from a quotation; full stop, exclamation mark and question mark are used at the end of sentences but only one at a time; and quotation marks are used for citing direct speech (EUCLID 2021, 17).

I find that academic essay requires the use of several punctuations. The primary purpose is to make written communication correct and precise. Every language uses punctuation. English, the language of instruction in this course, requires meticulous punctuation. The two major variants of English are standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE).

3) LANGUAGE VARIANTS FOR ENGLISH WORLDS

I have interacted with the reading material, and there are words with different spellings, although they have identical pronunciations in both standard British English and American English. For example, Axe-ax; plough-plow; colour-color; centre-center; cheque-check; defence-defense; licence-license; Alright-all right; manoeuvre-maneuver; and tyre-tire (EUCLID 2021, 25). So when doing a literature search during review articles, it is better to include both variants. Also, once I find these words, I should not consider them different things when reading. In addition, I should restrict myself to either American or British English variants. Not knowing the English variants I use during academic essays is somewhat awkward. Notably, one should be conversant with both variants since some journals restrict to a particular English variant. Once I am well-versed in the chosen English variants, I must consider some selected words carefully.

Some words or nouns have different but similar spelling and pronunciation. I find that there is a need for me to exercise caution in scholarly writing when using these words. The words in English variants with different but similar spelling and pronunciation are

aluminium-aluminum, polythene-polyethylene; maths-math; and rise-raise in increasing wages (EUCLID 2021, 26). I have observed the difference in using American or British variants of English in large collective nouns.

I have found that Standard American English uses the singular form, unlike standard British English, which uses the plural for large collective nouns (EUCLID 2021, 27). Correctly using punctuation can differentiate between the variant of American and British English.

In punctuation, I find that SAE uses double quotation marks, whereas SBE uses single quotations. If there is a quotation within a quotation, SAE uses a single quotation inside, whereas SBE uses a double quotation within the quotation. Commas or periods are always inside the quotation marks in SAE, whereas for SBE, the commas or periods can be either inside or outside the quotation marks (EUCLID 2021, 32). I must take care when complying with a given writer's style. In any case, it can be better to always put the punctuation inside the quotation as a generalization. Similarly, punctuations also vary with formal letters.

A formal letter is typical in academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 32); for example, when writing a cover page to the editor, and inquiry for a research grant, in SAE, the salutation will be Dear Dr. Kepa: unlike in SBE, Dear Dr Kepa, This is also applicable in writing, To whom it may concern: However, EUCLID recommend that title should not have any period the end.

The choice of any consistent language variant is very essential in academic writing. Therefore, when using standard American English in academic writing, I should study how it fits well in a style guide for any other chosen journals.

4) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide documents your approach to some aspects of writing style that must be consistent (EUCLID 2021, 41). I need to review my written information, come up with my approach, and use it consistently. It will make my work easy to execute and review precisely. There are many types of writing using a style guide. Among them are technical writing, commercial writing, journalism, and web copywriting (EUCLID 2021, 41). In all, there is a need for consistency.

Different aspects of style guides exist in scholarly writing. These aspects vary considerably among publications, journals, faculty, and school; they have their styles. Among the aspects are preferred sentence lengths; manuscript layout; font usage; depth of treatment of a subject; spelling, whether UK or US; readership consideration; use of abbreviations; acceptable terminology; the use of symbols; voice preferences consisting of passive or active; structure; paragraph numbering and indentation; the use of headings; the use of lists; trademarks and branding considerations (EUCLID 2021, 41–42). The style guide is more important in some situations than others.

Styles guide is essential in the following scenarios: ensuring consistency and coherence; providing basic rules; helping you learn and record what the customers prefer and then consequently their satisfaction, and you will become a supplier of choice (EUCLID 2021, 42). A style guide helps with documentation and ensuring that I master and conform to what is required. However, a good reference for a style guide can be challenging.

As much as most companies and publications have their own style guide, I can get good references for style from Strunk's "The element of style" and economical styles from the website (EUCLID 2021, 42).

A style guide is vital in academic writing. It can enforce citation, referencing, and avoiding plagiarism in several writing scenarios.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is using a source of information without giving credit to the original author (EUCLID 2021, 34). Accordingly, this can be in ideas, statistics, and visuals. Some authors also hand in their work used in different publications or settings. This practice is also plagiarism. Plagiarism can land a scholar severe academic problems.

It is unethical and wrong to use somebody's work and fail to recognize them for their efforts. Not only that, it is unfair to do so. Someone has invested a lot of time and resources and sacrificed to do all the work for you to copy and paste to deceive others that it is yours! In any case, plagiarizing other authors' works is a grave academic offense. This vice can lead to penalties. As a result of this, it is better to avoid plagiarism.

To avoid plagiarism, we must cite the source of the information we have paraphrased or quoted. Citation is the method used to indicate where the information is coming from (EUCLID 2021, 34). There are two critical things in the citation; paraphrasing and quotation. Always cite paraphrased and quoted information correctly. Paraphrased statements must include the author in the parenthesis. You can start with a signal phrase in the quotation, and the quotation must have quotation marks unless the quotation occupies more than four lines where you use indentation without quotation marks (EUCLID 2021, 35). Here, the parenthesis will have only the page number. Often it is better to limit quotations; otherwise, the work will look like it is not yours. In such a case, it is better to paraphrase and accordingly cite instead (EUCLID 2021, 34).

Cite all the paraphrases and quotations. Otherwise, you fall into a vice of plagiarism. In some instances, one may not cite when the information is common knowledge, such as mycobacteria tuberculosis causes tuberculosis. If you do not know whether the information is common knowledge, you need to check, and if you find it coming from numerous sources, then it is a piece of common knowledge, and you should not cite it (EUCLID 2021, 37). All information cited should be inserted in the bibliography.

The items cited should be listed in the bibliography or references. A bibliography summarizes all the information on the publication from which one takes the information (EUCLID 2021, 38). In the bibliography, one finds the details about the source of the work cited. I find one can use a bibliography and references interchangeably. In an academic essay, it is crucial to reference the information taken from other authors.

6) REFERENCING

Referencing is an essential part of academic essay writing. It guards against plagiarism. While reading the ACA-401D course pack, I found that all academic essays must have references (EUCLID 2021, 11). Once referencing is not done, it implies that one's written work is solely his or hers. However, if one scrutinizes the work further, one will realize that some other persons could have done similar writing before, and the writer could have borrowed some information from them. It would be prudent to cite all the works that the writer comes across during the reading except the common knowledge, and also, one must read other works done before because new knowledge builds on the existing knowledge. In an academic essay, omitting referencing leads to academic penalties.

Failure to insert references in academic essays can land me severe academic offenses, referred to as plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 11). One such penalty is mark reduction. For example, teaching staff from one of the four Australian universities in Singapore cited a student who used his previous work and submitted it for marking without referencing it. The Lecturer detected it and awarded a lower mark than what he got from the prior assignment (Palmer 2021, 17). Considering this, I find that if I fail to properly cite the source of information I use from others' work, I will have my marks deducted. I may end up repeating the whole period or even disqualify from the course.

To avoid being penalized, I find it better to obtain the preferred referencing style for each school, faculty, or journal (EUCLID 2021, 11). Some of these authorities accept more than one referencing style. For instance, EUCLID takes any style provided they are consistently applied.

Referencing plays a crucial role in academic writing. I find it a good practice to acknowledge authors for their publications. Therefore, I always cite the work of other authors during academic writing.

Since referencing plays a vital role in academic writing, I find it a good practice to acknowledge authors for their actions. This culture makes me always consider referencing as a critical thing during academic writing.

7) CONCLUSION

Overall, the academic writing coursepack as an introductory course enables me to learn to write effectively during this doctoral training. It encompasses many facets such as punctuation, language variants for English worlds, style guide, plagiarism, and referencing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Palmer, Anne. 2021. "Investigating Staff Views on Plagiarism in Transnational Higher Education." *Journal of Applied Learning and Teaching* 4, no. 2: 17.

Rozell, Daniel. 2022. "Citation Styles of References: A Weakness of Academic Publishing." *European Science Editing* 48: e79945.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.